

The Level of Customer Service Satisfaction of Selected Airbnb in Mandaluyong City

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Abstract: “Airbnb (Air Bed and Breakfast) is a service that allows property owners rent out their spaces to travelers looking for a place to stay”. With the worldwide success of this type of lodging service, the researchers were inspired to conduct a study that is focused on Airbnb, particularly on the level of customer satisfaction on the quality of service provided by this type of lodging facility. The study employed the descriptive method of research. The approach was quantitative since the problems posed in the study were expressed in numerical data obtained from the survey conducted through questionnaires. There was a total of 102 guests from the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City who were randomly selected and participated in the study. They were asked on their perception as to the service quality provided by the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City. Their perception was also determined in terms of booking procedures, host reception, accommodation, price, location. The demographic characteristics of the participants were also taken to find out if they are significantly related to their satisfaction with Airbnbs’ quality of service. Likewise, the relationship between service quality and satisfaction was also determined.

Based on the results of the study, the quality of service provided by Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City was very good in terms of booking procedures, accommodation, host reception, price, and location. It was determined that guests’ satisfaction on the quality of service provided depends on the educational attainment of the guests but not on their age, gender, monthly income, and civil status. It was also found out that satisfaction of the guests is strongly correlated with the quality of service received from the Airbnbs. Lastly, as part of the output, the researchers developed a set of recommendations to help improve and increase the level of guest satisfaction on the service quality provided by the selected Airbnbs.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Airbnbs, Service Quality, Lodging.

1. INTRODUCTION

Service quality and customer satisfaction are critical for the service survival. These are the main components that should be provided by companies to be able to survive in the hospitality industry. Service quality in the hospitality industry has become one of the most important factors for gaining competitive advantage as well as customers’ confidence and satisfaction in this highly competitive industry.

Furthermore, customer satisfaction and service quality are the main factors to be considered in lodging operations in determining the stability of a business and the relationship towards its guests. Getting customer feedback regarding their satisfaction can be done through personal surveys and on-site interviews. Through the years, new ways of measuring customer satisfaction are emerging, and one of them is through online ratings wherein guests can directly write their comments and rate the establishment based on their personal experience.

Because the needs and expectations of customers are continuously changing, one must always be “in-the-know” and be constantly updated with what is happening in the market. Companies must be able to remain strong and competitive in the field of hospitality. And as new trends arise, a lot of strategies were created, and new ways of accommodating guests have emerged and one of the most successful trends in the lodging industry is the Air Bed-and-Breakfast or Airbnb.

Airbnb is an online community marketplace where people can list any accommodation for rent and others can book the space for use. Designers Joe Gebbia, Brian Chesky, and Nathan Blecharczyk founded Airbnb in 2008. Airbnb lodgings, which can range from a single room or apartment to a castle or yacht, could be found in over 81,000 Cities and 192 countries around the world (Sraders, A., 2018). Airbnb has brought a new meaning into lodging operations and within a small span of time it has already boomed. A lot of people prefer to stay in Airbnb rather than in hotels especially those guests who are after the price and the convenience it offers. As a matter of fact, based on Airbnb Newsroom (2019), Airbnb has hosted 400 million guests since its launch. With its affordable price and convenience, guests were easily attracted to this new lodging trend.

Since Airbnb is a type of lodging operations that rely heavily on technology, particularly on the internet in doing their business, there are some areas which are considered to be crucial to its operations. These include the online reservation and booking system, service/product inclusions, its accommodation facilities, price, and location. This is also one of the reasons why the researchers got interested to conduct a study that is focused on the delivery of quality service of Airbnb’s and the level of customer satisfaction.

To better monitor the operations of Airbnb in the Philippines, the Philippine Tourism Act and its Implementing Rules and Regulations provides specific regulations on how Private Homes or Homestays may be used to provide accommodation for tourists. Moreover, the Code on Sanitation of the Philippines, on the other hand, sets rules for sanitation practices for accommodation establishments and hotels throughout the country.

At present, the Department of Tourism has started accrediting local properties offered on the Airbnb booking platform, a step that enables the national government to regulate the business and collect taxes from them (<https://businessstar.com.ph>, 2021).

All this valuable information, data, and statistics have increased awareness and interest of the researchers on Airbnb which led to the decision to conduct this study entitled, “The Level of Customer Service Satisfaction of Selected Airbnb in Mandaluyong City”. Why in Mandaluyong City? Primarily because there is a big number of Airbnbs in this city. Presently, the current number of Airbnbs operating in Mandaluyong City numbers around 300.

With all these relevant studies conducted on Airbnb, the researchers were more encouraged to investigate how the quality of service provided by Airbnb affect the satisfaction level of the guests/customers. Furthermore, the researchers would like to contribute to the Airbnb sector. Through this study, the researchers will share the results, as well as the recommended strategies, to the Airbnb owners/operators so that they will be able to evaluate the areas where they can improve on and increase the level of their customer satisfaction. This can also be a tool for the Airbnb owners/operators to market their products and services to other potential customers who would want to avail of their services in the future.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The researchers used the Independent-Dependent framework to show the relationship between variables. In this study, the independent variables are the demographic profile and the respondent’s perceptions on customer service provided by Airbnb. The dependent variable is the level of customer satisfaction.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The primary purpose of the study was to explore the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction. The researchers would like to know how satisfied the customers are with the quality of service provided by Airbnb. Moreover, the researchers also determined the reasons behind why customers avail the services and prefer to stay in Airbnb rather than in other lodging facilities.

Specifically, the researchers aimed to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms:
 - 1.1 of age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 marital status;
 - 1.4 educational attainment;
 - 1.5 employment status; and
 - 1.6 income level?
2. What are the perceptions of the respondents on the quality of service provided by Airbnb in terms of:
 - 2.1 booking procedures;
 - 2.2 accommodations;
 - 2.3 price;
 - 2.4 location; and
 - 2.5 host reception?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their perception on the quality of service provided by Airbnb?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the quality of service provided by Airbnb and customer satisfaction?
5. Based on the results, what strategies can be recommended to improve the quality of service among the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City?

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESES

The null hypotheses were stated as follows:

H1: There is no significant relationship between the demographic profile of respondents and their perception on the quality of service provided by Airbnb?

H2: There is no significant relationship between the quality of service provided by Airbnb and customer satisfaction.

This study was conducted to measure the level of customer satisfaction with respect to service quality dimensions. Hence, the researchers have taken a case study on Hotel Silver Palace of Jalgaon City in Maharashtra (Anawade, P.A. and Bendale, S. K., 2016). This paper analyzed the importance of customer satisfaction which was carried out with the help of quantitative research by using a questionnaire which was designed on keeping in mind the basic of customer satisfaction.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer satisfaction is nothing but the outcome of a cognitive and effective evaluation, where some standard expectation is compared to the perceived performance. If the customer's perceived performance is less than expected, customers will be dissatisfied. On the other hand, if the perceived performance exceeds expectations, customers will be satisfied (Anawade, P.A., Bendale, S. K., 2016).

In the marketing perspective, for a consumer to achieve a degree of satisfaction, it is necessary for the product or service to be of a high degree of quality and to meet the needs of consumers with their performance (Hwang & Seo, 2016). Consequently, in the hospitality and in other tourism service context, the research of Ahrholdt, et al., (2017) established the purpose of service quality as a referent to customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction as a referent to loyalty.

In the recent hospitality trends, the peer-to-peer (P2P) accommodation happens when a person rents an apartment or a room he/she owns to other persons, which is typically enabled by digital platforms such as Airbnb. As a peer-to-peer network, Airbnb allows individuals to rent from private owners for a certain fee. Among the requirements as per Philippine Department of Tourism (DOT) for the accreditation of Airbnbs are as follows:

1. Compliance to Health and Safety requirements;
2. Compliance to Covid-19 related protocols and regulations;
3. Compliance to Tax Laws of the Bureau of Internal Revenue.
4. In addition to the above, Airbnbs are required to submit to DOT the following documents for accreditation:
 - a. Letter of intent to operate indicating therein the nature of their operations;
 - b. Accomplished Application Form;
 - c. Accomplished Self-Assessment Form;
 - d. Valid Mayor's or Business Permit;
 - e. Sworn Statement of Undertaking

Aside from these accreditation requirements, there are other factors that customers consider when booking/reserving for an Airbnb. Generally, customers of Airbnb consider the price as one of the major reasons for their choice of accommodation. Heo and Hyun (2015) stated that certain amenities affect the price in the traditional hospitality section, hence it is hypothesized that certain amenities will also affect price in the sharing economy of Airbnb.

Experiencing high-quality, idle resources (e.g., spare rooms or unoccupied houses) at a lower price gives consumers of peer-to-peer sharing systems a higher satisfaction. Based on two studies with users of Car2Go and Airbnb, Möhlmann (2015) confirms that cost-savings positively influence satisfaction and intention to use Airbnb again in the future.

Further studies on customer satisfaction with the use of Airbnb include that of Tussyadiah and Zach (2016) who stated that amenities and convenience of location are important attributes for guest evaluation with Airbnb accommodation. Therefore, it is argued that the benefits from Airbnb accommodation amenities and location, representing utility and service quality, contribute to guest satisfaction and their intention to use the services again in the future.

Moreover, Guttentag, 2015; Kim et al., (2015), stated other influencing factors of satisfaction of Airbnb accommodation. One of which is the location which allows for a more local and less touristic experience, and access to a variety of local amenities. The location and amenities are attributes that most stand out, contributing on a large scale to guest satisfaction and the intention to acquire the services in the future.

The study of D. Guttentag (2015) was strongly supported by Tussyadiah and Pesonen (2016) who further concluded that customer satisfaction concerning peer-to-peer accommodation, specifically Airbnb was essentially determined by monetary benefits, accommodation attributes (location, host reception, and comfort of accommodation) and the fun that resulted from the whole experience.

According to S.R. Pascoal-Barbosa (2019), location was the most valued aspect by customers regarding Airbnb. The location attributes include transportation availability, nearness to tourist attractions, supermarkets, and restaurants, as well as location-related safety issues. The second aspect is the host and his quick response to customer inquiries. It was followed by accommodations (facilities and amenities) provided. Fourth is the traditional experience of “living as a local”. And the last factor is price. All these factors contributed to satisfaction of customers who frequently avails Airbnb services.

Based on the study of Weng (2016), there are five factors in hotel and other accommodation facilities which are deemed to be important to customers. These are: brand, price, product quality, service quality, and prestige. Out of these factors, service quality and price are considered to be the top factors that determined customers’ overall satisfaction. Service quality has been identified as the most influential factor making it appeared that customers are not simply looking for basic services and quality provided by a hotel but more on the expectation of a high standard of personal service. Hoteliers must ensure the quality of service through constant review of customers’ needs and by strengthening customer service training programs for their employees. Crucial also to the quality of service is internal marketing. Treating employees in the same way as customers would enhance employees’ satisfaction, which is fundamental good service provision to customers. Other factors that must not be ignored are brand, price, product quality, and prestige. Although these are found to be less important in influencing satisfaction, they are important in maintaining the standards of these services and facilities to meet the basic needs of the customers. The absence or failure in these factors to meet customers’ desires could result in dissatisfaction.

Mim & Ferdous (2020) further explained that customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hospitality industry is impacted by explicit product or service highlights and impression of value. Satisfaction is additionally affected by customers’ passionate reactions, their attributions’ view of value. The key factors found to be very important and affective to gain customers’ satisfaction and loyalty are service quality, price, location and atmosphere, and consumer behavioral intentions.

Finally, Almeida & Pelissari (2019) said that rooms, service, value for money, cleanliness, sleep quality, and location can influence customer satisfaction in a hotel or in any accommodation facility. However, this may vary according to the type of traveler and category of the standard room price.

3. METHODOLOGY

This presented an outline of research methods that was applied in the study. The researcher described the research design for the purpose of this study and the reasons for the choice of the said design. The instrument used for data collection was also described. The researchers also discussed the methods used in analyzing the data. Lastly, the interpretation and analysis of data results were also presented.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The researchers used the Quantitative-Descriptive method to determine the level of customer satisfaction in relation to the service quality provided in selected Airbnb in Mandaluyong City. Descriptive method of research is used in the study since the researchers aimed to describe a certain situation/event at the time the study was conducted. This situation/event is the level of customer satisfaction on the service quality provided by the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City. The study is descriptive in nature since this involved the collection of data in order to test a hypothesis or to describe the current status of the subject of the study. The study is quantitative in approach since the problems posed in this research are answered in terms of numerical/statistical figures.

RESEARCH LOCALE

Airbnb has become popular internationally as well as locally and one specific city in the Philippines where there are many Airbnb facilities is Mandaluyong City. The researchers gathered data in selected Airbnb in Mandaluyong City because it is a 1st class highly urbanized city in Metro Manila as to which a lot of guests prefer to stay in Airbnb because it is closer to many tourist attractions and business centers.

There are 300 Airbnbs currently operating in Mandaluyong City. Out of these 300, one hundred (100) were chosen for the reason that these are the ones with the highest number of guests accommodated in the previous years. From these 100 Airbnbs, the researchers were able to gather one (1) participant per Airbnb with the exception of two Airbnbs that had two (2) respondents.

PARTICIPANTS OF THE STUDY

There was a total of 102 respondents in the study. These were guests who have stayed and availed the services of the selected 100 Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City.

The participants/guests considered in the study were those who frequently availed of the accommodations of Airbnbs in the city. Most of them are young urban professionals and single. They were chosen since they were the ones who have more direct exposure and have experienced the services provided by the Airbnbs in Mandaluyong.

DATA SAMPLING

The researchers included 102 respondents through purposive sampling to produce results that are representative of the whole population.

Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a non-probability technique in which the researchers rely on their own judgment in choosing the members of the population to be included in the survey. Usually, this type of sampling is used in very small sample sizes as in this study. This method is used here to make it easy for the researchers to make a generalization a sample being compared to, example, a random sample where not all participants have the same characteristics one is studying.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT & DATA GATHERING PROCEDURES

The researchers developed a survey questionnaire to serve as an instrument for primary data collection. The questionnaire was divided into three parts; the first part determined the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part focused on the perceptions of the respondents on the service quality provided by Airbnb in the aspects of booking, accommodations, price, location, and host reception. And the last part analyzed the impacts of service quality to the level of customer satisfaction. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, in this case, the guests/customers of the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City.

With the help of the survey questionnaires, the data was gathered from the guests who have stayed in the selected Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City. It was handed out by the Airbnb owners/operators to their customers who answered the survey and returned to the owner when they were done. Once all the questionnaires have been answered, the researchers collected the forms from the Airbnb owners.

DATA TREATMENT & ANALYSIS

Responses to the questionnaires by the Airbnb guests were tallied and statistically analyzed in line with the data requirement of the study. Quantitative analysis techniques were employed to show the processed data in absolute terms using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency, percentages, minimum and maximum value, and chi-square test for analyzing the relationship.

Frequency/Percentage is used in the description of the demographic characteristics of the participants.

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where P- percentage

f- frequency

n- number of participants

Mean, which is a measure of central tendency, is used to give a summary of the characteristics of a group (satisfaction level).

$$X = \sum wx/n$$

Where X- weighted mean

w- weight of each observation

x- number of observations

n- total number of observation

Chi square test of association is a test used to determine the significance of the relationship between two variable-demographic characteristics and quality of service.

$$X^2 = (O-E)^2/E$$

Where X²- chi square value

O- observed frequency

E- expected frequency

Lastly, the results, findings, and recommendations will be shared with the Airbnb owners/operators so that they will be able improve the quality of their service and increase customer satisfaction.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1 Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Rank
18-25	53	52.0	1
26-33	40	39.2	2
34-41	8	7.8	3
42-49	1	1.0	4
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows that the highest percentage in the age bracket would be the respondents who were between 18-25 with an average of 52%, and the lowest would be those between 42-49 with an average of 1%.

This age of 18-25 years old are the usual ages of young urban professionals who are considered in the study.

This finding is in contradiction with the finding in US and Europe that majority of the Airbnb users there are between the ages of 25-34 years old. However, it is in line with the findings that people in older age groups made up a smaller share of Airbnb users (<https://statistica.com>, 2019).

Table 1.2 Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Rank
No response	2	2.0	3
Female	47	46.1	2
Male	53	52.0	1
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows that most of the respondents are male, which is 52%, followed by the female which is 46.1%.

Male guests outnumber females due to that fact that the former value privacy less than the latter.

In light of the recent negative coverage against Airbnb's where instances of the hosts installing hidden cameras to watch guests, hence, male guests who do not value privacy too much as compared to women who are less likely to check-in at Airbnbs (Mest, 2017) due to privacy concerns.

Table 1.3 Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Married	26	25.5	2
Single	76	74.5	1
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows that most of the respondents are single with an average of 74.5% followed by married respondents with an average of 25.5%

This is so because most of the respondents were just 18-25 years old, it is natural that most of them are singles.

This is contradictory to the findings made by Ganapathi & Vethirajan (2020), which shows that married tourists are more likely to check-in at hotels as compared to singles. But the result proves that single travelers are most likely to avail the services of Airbnbs rather than that of hotels.

Table 1.4 Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Associate degree graduate	3	2.9	3
Bachelor's degree graduate	81	79.4	1
High school graduate	18	17.6	2
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows that most of the respondents are graduates with a Bachelor's Degree with an average of 79.4%, and the lowest average are those with an associate degree with an average of 2.9% out of 100%.

Young urban professionals are more likely to have Bachelors' degree. This explains why most of the participants in the study are college degree holders.

This is in accordance to the findings of Ganapathi and Vethirajan (2020) which stated that most hotel guests are either in the college level or have post college degree.

Table 1.5 Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Permanent	72	70.6	1
Probatory	16	15.7	2
Contractual	14	13.7	3
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows the distribution of the participants in terms of their employment status, most of them at 70.6% are permanent in their positions. Only 15.7% are probationary waiting for 6 months before they can be permanent in their positions pending evaluation of their job performance while 13.7% are only contractual which means that they are under 6 months contract only.

The result is in line with that in Table 1.4. Since most of the guests of Airbnbs are bachelor's degree graduates, it is expected that they already have permanent jobs and a more stable career. Also, these guests are those who are more knowledgeable of the Airbnbs services and rates and would prefer this type of lodging facilities.

Table 1.6 Income Level

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent	Rank
No response	26	25.5	2
Below Php 20,000	16	15.7	3
Php 20,000 to Php34,999	40	39.2	1
Php 35,000 to Php 49,999	14	13.7	4
Php 50,000 to Php 64,999	3	2.9	5.5
Over Php 65,000	3	2.9	5.5
Total	102	100.0	

The table shows that most respondents' monthly income ranges between Php 20,000 – Php 34,999 with an average of 39.2%, and the lowest average is the respondents with a higher income ranging from Php 50,000 – Php 64,999 and those with income above Php 65,000, both with an average of 3%.

Considering the accommodation rates of Airbnbs, only those with average monthly income can afford this as seen in the table above.

This is aligned with Hubner, et al., (2021) that says that demographics of customers including monthly income have effect on the perception of the customers in availing hotels accommodation with only those with income that are above the average can avail of hotels,

2. Perceptions of the Respondents on the Quality of Service of Airbnb

Table 2.1 Booking Procedures

Booking/Reservation Procedures	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. There is a wide listing of Airbnb available	3.25	.539	Agree
2. Complete information was provided	3.23	.486	Agree
3. The host's reply on my booking inquiries was quick	3.23	.543	Agree
4. Payment methods and policies were clearly stated	3.21	.494	Agree
5. Cancellation and refund policies were clearly stated	3.21	.474	Agree
6. The booking procedure was organized and quick	3.20	.508	Agree

In terms of booking procedures, respondents showed the highest mean of agreement in the provision of complete information and in readiness of the hotel to respond to inquiries. The lowest mean, on the other hand, is seen in the organized and quick booking procedure.

This is the same with Ganapathi, et. al., (2020) that said agreement (3.14) to the quickness of service including booking as a factor in the satisfaction of tourists towards hotels.

Table 2.2 Accommodations

Accommodation	Mean	Deviation	Interpretation
1. The whole building and rooms were clean and well-lighted	3.38	.598	Agree
2. The facilities/furniture/fixtures in the room were in good condition and working properly	3.31	.580	Agree
3. Basic/essential room supplies were available	3.40	.601	Agree
4. The bedroom was spacious	3.28	.552	Agree
5. The bathroom was clean and has basic/essential toiletries	3.34	.589	Agree
6. There is a spacious parking lot provided	3.31	.580	Agree

On the aspect of accommodation, respondents showed agreement in all indicators with the highest mean on the availability of basic room supplies. The lowest mean of agreement is seen on the space of the bedrooms. This is in line with Ganapathi et. al., (2020) that said that hotel guests agreed that room amenities is a factor in their satisfaction (mean=3.85) and in the cleanliness and space of rooms (mean=3.84).

In summary, majority of the respondents Agree that the selected Airbnb in Mandaluyong City provided the accommodations that the consumers expected, the complete amenities of the room, the spacious unit, and the cleanliness and comfortability of the place.

Table 2.3 Price

Price	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The price is within my budget	3.35	.591	Agree
2. The price matches the standard of services and facilities provided	3.33	.586	Agree
3. The price is worth the money spent/paid for	3.34	.554	Agree
4. Price is cheaper than nearby hotels and other lodging facilities	3.35	.557	Agree
5. There are no hidden charges or additional fees required upon check-in	3.36	.559	Agree
6. The total amount/price was computed accurately	3.31	.563	Agree

The table shows that the respondents agree to all the indicators related to price. The highest mean is on the indicator saying that there are no hidden charges or additional fees upon checking in. The lowest mean is on the accurate computations of the total amount price.

Ganapathi et. al., (2020) stated that room tariff is one parameter of measuring the satisfaction of guests (mean=3.23). Price is also one of the top two factors important in measuring the satisfaction of the customers according to Weng (2016).

Overall, the respondents Agree that the Price is one of the main factors in choosing Airbnb as their type of accommodation. The data showed that the price had influenced the host's affordable price and the offers that match the budget.

Table 2.4 Location

Location	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The location and surrounding areas are well-lighted and safe	3.24	.548	Agree
2. The location is accessible and visible	3.26	.506	Agree
3. The location is near to other tourist attractions	3.18	.496	Agree
4. The location is near to convenience stores, food establishments and other business outlets	3.25	.521	Agree
5. There are several public transportation vehicles available within the area	3.24	.511	Agree
6. There are enough information and directional signage provided in the area	3.28	.552	Agree

As shown in Table 2.4, respondents agreed that location is an important factor in the selection of hotel and in guaranteeing guests' satisfaction. Highest mean of agreement is seen in accessibility and visibility of the hotel. The lowest mean is seen in the nearness of the hotel to tourist attractions.

The importance of location of the hotel in the satisfaction of the guests was also seen in Ganapathi et. al., (2020) where location plays a role in guest satisfaction with a mean of 3.90.

Based on the results, majority of the respondents Agree that Location of Airbnb can affect their decision as to where they would stay. If the location has all the features such as: accessibility to nearby tourist attractions, malls, restaurants, banks, convenience stores, and public transportation are available around the area, then it would be a good place to choose where they would stay.

Table 2.5 Host Reception

Host Reception	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Communicating with the host (thru text, call, messenger, e-mail) is always easy	3.24	.548	Agree
2. The host was willing and able to answer my inquiries	3.23	.543	Agree
3. The host responded quickly to my questions/concerns	3.19	.502	Agree
4. The host was polite/respectful during all our conversation	3.23	.543	Agree
5. The host provided me with true and honest information	3.24	.530	Agree
6. The host provided and delivered all that was promised to me	3.25	.521	Agree

With regards to Airbnbs' host reception, the respondents agreed to all the indicators in this aspect signifying satisfaction in terms of reception of host. The highest mean of agreement is seen in the delivery and fulfillment of the promises made by Airbnb. The lowest mean is manifested in the quick response of the host to any queries by the guest.

This is in line again with Ganapathi et al. (2020) saying that quickness of service promises and host responses to queries is a factor in guest satisfaction (mean=3.17)

Also, based on findings, users feel that real experience is one of the things that has affected their satisfaction with Airbnb.

According to the statistics, many respondents agree that the host provides and delivers on what they offer to the guest. According to the findings of this survey, most people who booked Airbnb accommodations in Mandaluyong City are Filipinos. These respondents are at ease staying in the homes of their fellow Filipinos since they are all considered to be welcoming. This characteristic increased the probability of a guest selecting Airbnb because there is no doubt about the host's service and personality.

Many respondents also believe that the Airbnb host does not quite reply quickly to customer questions/concerns, which is the least of all the indications. Filipinos are well known for being hospitable. Therefore, selecting a fellow Filipino as their host is an excellent choice for the Filipino guest.

3. Relationship Between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and Their Perception on the Quality of Service

Table 3. Respondent's Demographic Profile & their Perception on the Quality of Service

Demographic Profile	Chi-square statistic value	df	p-value	Interpretation/Implication
Gender	1.943	4	0.746	Not Significant/ The perception of respondents does not depend on gender
Marital Status	0.6	2	0.741	Not Significant/ The perception of respondents does not depend on marital status
Age	3.934	6	0.686	Not Significant/ The perception of respondents does not depend on age
Educational Attainment	7.784	4	0.096	Not Significant/ The perception of respondents does not depend on educational attainment
Employment Status	10.585	4	0.032*	Significant/The perception of the respondents depends on the employment status
Monthly Income	11.781	10	0.300	Not Significant/ The perception of respondents does not depend on monthly income

*Significant

The table shows the results of the chi square test of association in determining whether there exists a significant relationship between demographic profile of the respondents and their perception on the quality of service.

It is shown here that age is not significantly related to perception on the quality of service as manifested in its p-value of 0.686 which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This is also the same in gender with p-value of 0.746; in educational attainment with p-value of .096; and monthly income with p-value of 0.30. These mean that the perception on quality of service does not depend on age, gender, educational attainment, and monthly income. However, it was found here that service quality perception depends on employment status with a p-value of .032 which is less than .05 significance level.

The findings on gender and employment are contrary to Juliana, et al (2021) saying that both have significant effect on customers perceived value of service quality. The findings on the effect of age which is not significant on the perception on service quality is like Juliana, et al. (2021).

Monthly income was found in the study of Ganapathi & Vethirajan (2020) to have a significant effect in the perception of service quality of hotels in South Tamil Nadu. This is contrary to findings of this study. This is also the same with the findings on educational attainment to have a significant effect on perceived service quality.

In terms of employment status, there is a significant relationship between respondents' satisfaction and their perception of respondents in Airbnb Mandaluyong City. In addition, this research shows that the pricing satisfaction of guests affected their job status. Furthermore, the results indicated that they prefer Airbnb as a place to stay based on their work position and monthly income. Therefore, these data show that they picked Airbnb to stay based on their job position.

Aside from that, there is no significant statistical relationship between the demographic and the other factors: gender, marital status, age, educational attainment, monthly income, and respondents' perception of Airbnb in Mandaluyong City. Spearman's rho was used to measure the relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and customer satisfaction. Thus, the Significant relationship exists at 0.01 level (two-tailed).

Overall, the pricing was well received by the responders. The price of lodging is the most important factor for guests. Airbnb provides sleeping space, a single room, a complete unit, or an entire house. The demographic profiles of these respondents revealed that most of them are between the ages of 18 and 25; they are also known as millennials. On the other hand, respondent is least satisfied by the location. According to the data, aside from the price and accommodation, most of the respondents are leisure travelers where Mandaluyong City is near some establishment such as SM Megamall, San Felipe Church, Shangri-la Manila, etc. this location is perfect for the guests for leisure, and it is a perfect place to hang out. Also, there is accessible public transportation for them to get there. As shown in the results, the respondents agreed with the procedures of the Booking/Reservation Procedures of Airbnb Mandaluyong. In addition, Airbnb provided the information that the guest needed to be informed about their reservation, rules, and policies.

4. Relationship Between Airbnb's Quality of Service and Customer Satisfaction

Table 4. Correlation Between Quality of Service & Customer Satisfaction

Correlations				
			Satisfaction	Quality of Service
Spearman's rho	Satisfaction	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.572**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	102	102
	Quality of Service	Correlation Coefficient	.572**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	102	102

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows that the correlation coefficient has a strong positive relationship between satisfaction and quality of service. The p-value of 0.000 is less than the significance level of 0.01.

This means that if the quality of service is high, so is the level of satisfaction of the customers.

These findings are aligned with Johnson & Karlay (2018) that concluded that an improved service quality will significantly make customers happy and satisfied.

Overall, respondents were satisfied with the booking procedure, accommodations, pricing, location, and the cost approach. According to the research, most Airbnb Mandaluyong city respondents are Very Satisfied with the price of accommodations. The Airbnb cost given is appropriate for the guest's budget.

According to the statistics, most respondents are youths with paid jobs, which is one of the benefits of staying in Airbnb since it allows them to save much more money. Many respondents are also satisfied with the location because of its accessibility, which is the lowest of all the indicators.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers arrived at the following conclusions:

1. Majority of the participants in the study are aged between 18-25 years old. Most of them are male, single, and are bachelor's degree graduates, and have permanent employment status. Lastly, majority have a monthly income ranging from Php20,000 to Php34,999.

2. The perception on the quality of service provided by the selected Airbnb's are considered high/very good as manifested in their agreement to all the indicators under this aspect. This goes the same with accommodations, price, location, and host reception.

Based on the results, the selected Airbnbs provided the necessary information that the guests needed and that they agreed that the Booking/Reservation Procedures of Airbnbs in Mandaluyong City are efficient. Secondly, majority of the respondents agreed that the selected Airbnbs have provided their expected lodging services in terms of essential supplies and amenities, room cleanliness, and availability of basic facilities/furniture/fixtures. Moreover, in terms of the price, majority of the respondents, agreed that Airbnbs offer budget-friendly rates that they can afford and that there is no hidden or additional fees. This is one of the factors why most travelers choose this type of accommodations.

Furthermore, the respondents agreed that the Location of the selected Airbnbs are strategic with enough directional signages to guide them. Also, they agreed that the location is safe, visible, and accessible to nearby establishments and business outlets, as well as to public vehicle stations. Lastly, the respondents agreed that the Host provides and delivers what they promised to offer to the guest. Communication with the Host is easy and that they are provided with honest information. The Host is also polite and respectful and willing to answer inquiries. However, most of them perceived that the Host was not able reply quickly to guests' questions/concerns.

3. Guest satisfaction in Airbnb does not depend on gender, marital status, age, educational attainment, and monthly income. Hence, the null hypothesis on these specific demographic characteristics is accepted. However, satisfaction depends on employment status of the participants. Hypothesis rejection on employment status is taken.

4. The satisfaction of the guests of Airbnb's depends on the quality of service they perceived. There is a strong positive correlation between these two variables. This means that if the quality of service is very good, so is the satisfaction of the guests will be very high. Thus, the null hypothesis on this is therefore rejected.

The respondents were satisfied during their booking/ reservation procedures by having a quick and clear transaction. Indicated that they were satisfied in connection with the price of the accommodation offered in Airbnb, the cleanliness of the accommodation's location, the home experience they had during their stay, the interior design of the Airbnb unit, the accuracy of reservation when booking on the Airbnb platform, and the number of bedrooms about the size of accommodation. the cleanliness of the accommodation's location, the homely experience they had during their stay, the interior design of the Airbnb unit, the authenticity of the reservation when booking on the Airbnb platform, and the number of bedrooms appropriate to the size of the property.

In terms of the respondents' interpretation of quality service towards customer satisfaction, the results showed that the guests agree with the statements regarding the price offered by the host of Airbnb suits their expenditure, the location offered by Airbnb is safe, the host seems to be very hospitable and accommodating, and the accommodation is complete with amenities including such TV, cooking utensils, and other amenities; however, the researchers found that only respondents' employment status has a significant relationship with their perception. It is also indicated that it impacts which employed or unemployed guests are concerned regarding selecting Airbnb as their lodging, which affects their satisfaction.

According to the findings, there is a significant relationship between respondents' satisfaction with the price, location, authentic experience, variety of units, the convenience of booking, size of lodging in selecting Airbnb. As a result, respondents' perceptions about Airbnb impact their customer satisfaction with Airbnb.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The results showed that Airbnb have not yet reach their full potential in different areas namely accommodation, location, and host reception.

Airbnb owners and hosts should also take into consideration the following recommendations to improve and increase the satisfaction of guests towards Airbnb.

1. Provide discounts to the guest, especially if they are a returning guest, because this actually builds up the loyalty of the customer towards Airbnb.
2. The Airbnb host should give more time to interact and mingle with guests so that they can experience to live like a local at the location.

3. The host also needs to give attention to the detail of the room for example a strong Wi-Fi connection especially to those who are staying because of business purposes.
4. Airbnb owners can also include in their service a car rental service which the host can offer towards the customer especially that the area is near business centers.
5. Airbnb Host must also take into consideration the advantages and disadvantages of this type of accommodation mainly because Airbnb is increasingly gaining popularity towards the tourism sector of the country.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahrholdt, Dennis & Gudergan, Siggie & Ringle, Christian. (2017). *Enhancing Service Loyalty: The Roles of Delight, Satisfaction, and Service Quality*. *Journal of Travel Research*. 56. 436 - 450. 10.1177/0047287516649058.
- [2] Almeida & Pelissari(2019). *Customer Satisfaction based on the Attributes of Accommodation Services*. Retrieved from: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbtur/a/KwwDqmXG3npydzg4fqKD34b/?format=pdf&lang=en>
- [3] E Sthapit and J Jiménez-Barreto - Anatolia, (2018). *Sharing in the Host-Guest Relationship; Perspectives on the Airbnb Hospitality Experience*. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 2018. Taylor & Francis. Retrieved from:<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13032917.2018.1448876>
- [4] Ganapathi & Vethirajan. (2020). *A Study on the Factors Determining the Selection of Hotels Among Religious Tourist in South Tamil Nadu*. Retrieved from: https://ejmcm.com/article_7582_2a2f2fb9c0facef1ae6dced0a768bb8f.pdf
- [5] Guttentag, D. (2015). *Airbnb: Disruptive Innovation and the Rise of an Informal Tourism Accommodation Sector*. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 2015. Taylor & Francis
- [6] Heo, Cindy & Hyun, Sunghyup. (2015). *Do luxury room amenities affect guests' willingness to pay? International Journal of Hospitality Management*. 46. 10.1016/j.ijhm.2014.10.002.
- [7] Hubner et al. (2021). *Increased Preference and Value of Consumer Products by Attentional Selection*. Retrieved from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02086/full>
- [8] [\(2017\)](https://statistica.com)
- [9] Hwang, J. and Seo, S. (2016), "A critical review of research on customer experience management: Theoretical, methodological and cultural perspectives", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 28 No. 10, pp. 2218-2246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-04-2015-0192>
- [10] Jenkins, A. (2020). *Coping with a Bad Trip at Airbnb*. *Fortune*, 181(1), 66–75.
- [11] Johnson & Karlay (2016). *Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction*. Retrieved from: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1246475/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [12] Juliana et al., (2021). *Impact of Creativity and Innovation in Entrepreneurial Development*. Retrieved from: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=110573>
- [13] Mest, E. (2017). *How gender and safety play a role in Airbnb's popularity*. *Hotel Management*. Retrieved from: <https://www.hotelmanagement.net/operate/how-gender-and-safety-play-a-role-airbnb-s-popularity>
- [14] Mim & Ferdous (2020). *Factors influencing Customers Satisfaction in Hospitality Industry*. Retrieved from: [Divaportal.org/smash/get/diva2:1530554/FULLTEXT01.pdf](https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1530554/FULLTEXT01.pdf)
- [15] Möhlmann, M., (2015). *Collaborative consumption: Determinants of satisfaction and the likelihood of using a sharing economy option again*. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, ahead of print. doi: 10.1002/cb.1512
- [16] Nunes, Catarina Weber Bruxelas Sampaio, and Fie Frederiksen. "Amenities and Review Scores Behaviour on Host Price of AirBnB." *CBS Research Portal*, 2019. Retrieved from: <https://research.cbs.dk/en/studentProjects/ed557861-bd57-4b01-9e81-e5c05692dc21>
- [17] P.A Anawade, and Prof. Dr. Shilpa k. Bendale, *Customer Satisfaction with Reference to Individual Spending Pattern On Hotel Industry: A Case Study For Hotel Silver Palace*. *International Journal of Management*, 7(7), 2016, pp. 336–343.

- [18] Pascoal-Barbosa, S. R (2019). *A Dissertation on Airbnb Customer Satisfaction Thru Online Reviews*. Presented in ISCTE Business School, Instituto Universitario de Lisboa. September 2019.
- [19] Priporas, C-V., Stylos, N., Rahimi, R., & Vedanthachari, L. N. (2017). *Unraveling the diverse nature of service quality in a sharing economy: A social exchange theory perspective of Airbnb accommodation*. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(9), 2279-2301. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-08-2016-0420>
- [20] Priporas, C., Stylos, N., Vedanthachari, L. N., & Santiwatana, P. (2017). *Service quality, satisfaction, and customer loyalty in Airbnb accommodation in Thailand*. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(6), 693–704. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.2141>
- [21] Sraders, A. (2018, September 24). *How does airbnb work for hosts and travelers?* *TheStreet*. Retrieved July 18, 2022, from <https://www.thestreet.com/lifestyle/travel/how-does-airbnb-work-14714337>
- [22] Torrecampo et. al., (2000). *General Statistics made simple for Filipinos*. National Book Store. Navotas Press. Metro Manila. 2000.
- [23] Tussyadiah, I.P. (2016). *Factors of Satisfaction and Intention to Use Peer-to-Peer Accommodation*. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 55, 70-80. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2016.03.005>
- [24] Vujić, M., Đorđević, S., & Lakićević, M. (2019). *Service quality and customer satisfaction in the hotel industry in Serbia*. *Hotel & Tourism Management*, 7(1), 61. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5937/menhottur1901061V>
- [25] Wang et al. (2016). *The Relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction: The example of CJCU Library*. Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02522667.2006.10699686>